

Comparative Study of Adsorbents for Treatment of Industrial Effluent

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Abstract:

Water contaminated with various impurities is considered as wastewater and industrial wastewater obtained from industries is known as effluent. The industrial effluent adversely affects the aquatic ecosystems, deteriorate human health, and degrades overall environmental quality. Treatment of such effluent with adsorbent is one of the most efficient and cost-effective method. In the present study, industrial effluent was treated with various bio-adsorbents obtained from orange peels, cotton, neem tree bark. Effect of adsorption on parameters like pH, COD, BOD, TDS and TSS were determined and their results were compared with commercial grade activated charcoal. For majority of the parameters, the effectiveness of adsorbent varied as: activated charcoal > tree bark-based adsorbent > cotton-based adsorbent > orange peels-based adsorbent. Effect of pretreatment- acid treatment- was also examined for cotton and tree bark-based adsorbent. Phosphoric acid was proven to be better acid for pretreatment in comparison with sulfuric acid. For tree bark-based adsorbent treated with phosphoric acid, % removal for COD, BOD, TDS and TSS were 46.5 %, 57.06 %, 35.51% and 90.43% respectively.

Keywords: effluent, adsorbents, pre-treatment, removal efficiency.

1. Introduction

Industrial wastewater is a critical environmental concern nowadays, especially in areas experiencing rapid industrialization. Discharging untreated or inadequately treated industrial wastewater into water bodies has significant risks to aquatic life and human health. It contains a variety of pollutants, such as heavy metals, dyes, organic compounds, and other hazardous substances, which can lead to severe environmental and health problems.[1]

Traditional wastewater treatment methods, such as ion exchange, chemical precipitation, membrane filtration, aerobic and anaerobic processes, electrochemical methods, and agglomeration, are effective but come with high operational and maintenance costs. Additionally, these techniques often produce secondary pollutants that require further treatment and disposal. Consequently, there is a growing demand for sustainable and cost-effective solutions that can effectively remove pollutants from industrial effluent.

Low-cost adsorbents have become a viable option for addressing this problem. Usually, these adsorbents come from readily available and inexpensive sources, like natural materials (e.g., clay, zeolites), industrial by-products (e.g., fly ash, slag), and agricultural by-products (e.g., rice husk, sawdust).[2] In addition to lowering

wastewater treatment costs, using these materials encourages waste material recycling and reuse, which supports a circular economy.

The adsorption process, which is driven by chemical or physical interactions, causes contaminants to accumulate on the surface of the adsorbent material. Many contaminants, such as organic pollutants, dyes, and heavy metals, can be effectively eliminated with this approach. Adsorption efficiency is dependent upon several factors, including the adsorbent's surface area and porosity, the type of pollutants present, and the operational variables (pH, temperature, and contact time).[1,3]

While activated carbon and silica gel are the most commonly used conventional adsorbents, their high cost limits their extensive use.[4] Activated carbon, known for its high surface area and excellent adsorption capacity, is often considered the gold standard in adsorption processes. However, its production involves significant energy consumption and high operational costs, making it less feasible for large-scale applications, especially in developing regions. Similarly, silica gel, with its high porosity and surface reactivity, is effective but also expensive to produce and regenerate. Therefore, economic benefits, performance efficiencies, and environmental impact are crucial considerations when selecting an adsorbent. The search for cost-effective alternatives has led researchers to explore a variety of low-cost materials. These materials, often derived from natural sources or industrial and agricultural by-products, offer a sustainable solution to wastewater treatment. For instance, natural materials like clay and zeolites are abundant and inexpensive, providing a viable alternative to conventional adsorbents. Industrial by-products such as fly ash and slag, which are often considered waste, can be repurposed as adsorbents, thus reducing disposal costs and environmental impact.

Various studies have demonstrated that many relatively inexpensive materials can successfully remove pollutants from wastewater. For example, adsorbents prepared from agricultural by-products like rice husk, sawdust, and coconut shell have shown high adsorption capacities for heavy metals and organic pollutants[5]. These materials are not only cost-effective but also promote the recycling and reuse of agricultural waste, contributing to a circular economy. Additionally, adsorbents derived from industrial by-products like fly ash and slag have been found to effectively remove dyes and heavy metals from wastewater, offering a dual benefit of waste utilization and pollution control[5,6].

For instance, adsorbents prepared from materials like cotton, orange peels, and neem tree bark have shown promise in treating synthetic wastewater. Cotton, with its natural fibrous structure, provides a large surface area for adsorption. Orange peels, rich in pectin and cellulose, have been found to effectively adsorb heavy metals and dyes. Neem tree bark, known for its antimicrobial properties, offers additional benefits in treating wastewater containing pathogenic microorganisms.

However, there is limited research on the treatment of actual industrial effluent using these adsorbents, making this an area of unique and valuable study. Most studies have focused on synthetic wastewater, which may not accurately represent the complex mixture of pollutants found in industrial effluent. Therefore, further research is needed to evaluate the performance of these low-cost adsorbents in real-world conditions. In this study, adsorbents were prepared from inexpensive materials like cotton, orange peels, and neem tree bark and effect

on various parameters of industrial effluents were evaluated. Removal efficiency for these adsorbents were also studied.

2. Materials and Method

Fine activated carbon (AC) was purchased from Merck, particles having size < 0.15 mm were used to study the effect of activated charcoal on adsorption.

Adsorbent from Orange peels:

The orange peels were obtained from nearby fruit juice seller. The peels were chopped around 1-2 cm² rectangle shape, the thickness was measured about 3 mm. These chopped peels were washed with water to remove impurities on its surface and then sundried for a week, later it was dried in hot air oven over night to remove any moisture content. 20 ml of 98% concentrated H₂SO₄ was added to 20 g of dried peels and heated at 300 °C for 2 hours to allow charring [7]. As-synthesized charred orange peels were cooled and washed with distilled water several times to remove free acid content and dried in hot air oven at 85 °C for 2 hrs. As synthesized activated charcoal (OP) was used as adsorbent.

Adsorbent from wood outer layer bark:

1. Untreated tree bark (TB):

The neem bark was taken from the surroundings of, washed with warm water to remove impurities and then sundried for a week. The dried bark was later crushed and converted into small size particles which passes through 1.18 mm opening of sieve and retains on 0.6 mm opening of sieve. This untreated particle of tree bark (TB) was utilized as adsorbent.

2. Tree bark Treated with Sulphuric Acid (TBS):

Part of untreated tree bark prepared was mixed with 2 ml 98% concentrated H₂SO₄ per g of untreated bark. Same method mentioned earlier for orange peel sulphuric acid treatment was followed to synthesize sulphuric acid treated tree bark (TBS) as adsorbent.

3. Tree bark Treated with Phosphoric Acid (TBP):

Pretreatment of adsorbent with phosphoric acid was proven to efficient way to activating the adsorbent [8]. With this point, pretreatment of bark using phosphoric acid was analyzed. Part of untreated tree bark prepared was mixed with 5 ml 85% concentrated O-H₃PO₄ per g of untreated bark and allowed to swell at room temperature for 3 hours. This mixture was washed with distilled water several times to remove acid content and swollen bark can be obtained. The obtained phosphoric acid treated tree bark (TBP) was used as adsorbent.

Adsorbent made from Cotton:

The medical grade cotton was mixed with 86% concentrated H₃PO₄ such that all the cotton was wet by the phosphoric acid and allowed to swell at room temperature for 1 hour. Distilled water was added to this mixture to precipitate cotton and washed several times with distilled water to remove acid content. The produced swollen cotton was used as phosphoric acid treated cotton (COP).

The sand particles used for separating adsorbent layers was taken from construction site. The size of which was 0.15 – 0.3 mm (passing through 0.3 mm opening of sieve and retained on 0.15 mm opening of sieve).

The and was mixed with hot water and stirred for 15 min then filtered to remove impurities and later on washed with distilled water 2 times.

Analysis Methods:

Digital pH meter was used to measure pH of the samples. TDS was measured using TDS meter at room temperature. TSS were measured using gravimetric method. Open reflux titrimetric COD method was used for Chemical Oxygen Demand. BOD₃ was measured for all the samples. APHA/ AWWA standard were followed for preparing standard solutions/ reagents required for the above-mentioned tests. The chemical reagents used for above methods were of analytical grade.

Separate adsorbent beds were prepared for each adsorbent which is composed of alternate layers of adsorbent and sand in series repeated 3 times.

Fig 1: Schematic representation of adsorbent layered with sand

The effluent was first passed through single layer of sand to check if sand particle makes any significant effect on COD and BOD of industrial effluent. The resultant effluent obtained through the layer of sand had no significant change in said parameters hence sand particles behave as inert for the adsorption. The main role of sand particles is to separate the adsorbent layer and to increase residence time of effluent inside adsorbent bed.

3. Results and Discussion

Industrial effluent was stored in air tight container and various types of adsorbents were used to treat this effluent. Parameters like pH, BOD, COD, TDS, TSS were determined. The procedure was repeated thrice and average values were taken into consideration. Moreover, effect of pretreatment (Acid treatment- Sulfuric acid and Phosphoric acid) was also studied at depth. Initial values of water parameters were: pH – 5.43, COD – 2230 mg/L, BOD- 347 mg/L, TDS- 2506 mg/L and TSS- 564 mg/L.

3.1 Effect on pH

Effluent obtained from Industry was acidic in nature (pH – 5.43). After treating the effluent with adsorbent, pH of effluent was neutralized. pH values after adsorption were: AC- 7.45, OP- 7.11, CO- 7.32, COP- 6.96, TB- 6.79, TBS- 7.22 and TBP – 7.13.

3.2 Effect on COD

As shown in Fig 2, COD removal percentages are plotted against various adsorbents. It is clear from the plot that, maximum COD removal was obtained for AC as an adsorbent, followed by TB, CO and OP. Efficient COD removal was not achieved by CO, TB and OP but better removal was achieved. This difficulty in achieving higher removal percentage might be due to selective nature of adsorbent which selectively adsorbs molecules but wastewater effluent is basically mixture of various complex components.

Fig 2: COD removal percentage for various adsorbents

3.3 Effect on BOD

BOD of effluent decreased by treatment with various adsorbents. Removal efficiency achieved were 58.5 % for AC, 36.89 % for OP, 38.04 % for CO and 43.23% for TB (Fig 3). Maximum removal amongst synthetic adsorbent was for Tree bark - based adsorbent. Removal of BOD was also observed to be less due to the selective nature of adsorbent.

Fig 3: % BOD removal for AC, OP, CO and TB

3.4 Effect on TDS

TDS % removal varied nearly in the range of 21.95 % to 37.55 % for synthetic adsorbents and maximum for AC (37.55 %) (Fig 4).

Fig 4: Percentage TDS removal for different adsorbents

Such lesser removal might be due to presence of sand particles as bed component. Because of alternate layered structure of sand and adsorbent, sand was in contact with effluent water. Contact of sand and wastewater might have resulted in dissolution of salts (present in sand) in the effluent water. Due to presence of adsorbent, TDS dropped but due to contact of effluent with sand, TDS value raised. As a cumulative result, overall TDS removal percentage were in lower range. Lesser TDS removal indicates that such synthetic adsorbents are not efficient for removal of dissolved salt.

3.5 Effect on TSS

For all the variety of adsorbent, % TSS removal were almost in the range of 72 % to 95 %, maximum being for AC and minimum for CO (Fig 5). Very fine particles of AC helped to remove maximum suspended solids present in the effluent. Almost same results (~ 74 %) were obtained for CO and TB as adsorbents and the least (~72 %) TSS removal was achieved in case of OP as adsorbent. This was due to coarse particle size of OP in

comparison with CO and TB. Due to two layered structures of sand and adsorbents, higher % removal was achieved.

Fig 5: TSS removal for AC, OP, CO and TB

3.6 Effect of pretreatment

Higher removal was obtained for cotton and tree bark- based adsorption and due to this reason, effect of pretreatment was analyzed for these two adsorbents. Cotton and tree bark-based adsorbents were given acid treatment with sulfuric acid or phosphoric acid prior to using them for adsorption. Effect of phosphoric acid pretreatment on various parameters is shown in Fig 6(a) for cotton-based adsorbent. BOD, COD and TDS were significantly affected by acid pretreatment whereas for TSS, minor change in percentage removal was observed. Rise in activity due to pretreatment resulted in enhanced removal for BOD, COD and TDS.

(a) Effect of Pretreatment for CO

(b) Effect of Pretreatment for TB

Fig 6: (a) Effect of acid treatment on cotton as adsorbent and (b) Effect of acids treatment on tree bark as adsorbent

For tree bark-based adsorbent, effect of various acids- Sulfuric acid and Phosphoric acid- was also analyzed. It is clear from the graph (Fig 6 (b)) that, acid treatment enhanced the removal of COD, BOD, TDS and TSS and phosphoric acid was proven to be better in comparison with sulfuric acid. For COD and TDS, great change in removal efficiency was observed for acid treatment. On the contrary, only noticeable change in BOD values were obtained for the adsorbent pretreated with sulfuric acid and phosphoric acid.

4. Conclusion

Various types of adsorbents were successfully synthesized from inexpensive material and were utilized to treat industrial effluent. Major parameters like COD, BOD and TSS were reduced by treating effluent with synthesized adsorbents. Lesser removal of TDS was observed for all the types of adsorbents. For untreated as-synthesized adsorbents, tree bark-based adsorbent was the most efficient for the treatment of effluent. pH of the effluent was also neutralized with the help of adsorbent. Percentage removal was enhanced by pretreating the cotton and tree bark- based adsorbent with acid. Highest removal was obtained for tree bark-based adsorbent treated with phosphoric acid. Almost 12-17 % rise in all the parameters were obtained for tree bark- based adsorbent treated with phosphoric acid in comparison with untreated tree bark- based adsorbent. Moreover, it was observed that phosphoric acid was better to opt for pretreating the tree bark-based adsorbent. Removal efficiency of 46.5 %, 57.06 %, 35.51% and 90.43% were achieved for COD, BOD, TDS and TDS respectively. Overall, the study reveals that the low-cost adsorbents compete reasonably well with activated charcoal in terms of removal efficiency.

Acknowledgement:

Authors are thankful to Mr. Pratik Devani, Managing Director – Eco Earth Technologies, Ankleshwar for providing analytical facilities.

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